

Mass Psychology & Fascism: Le Bon and Freud and the Führer

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Introduction

This research is an interpretation study that uses the historical approach and compilation technique of Freud and Fuhrer's point of view. It is based on the Psychology of the Mass terminology that was pioneered by the French sociologist, social psychologist, and anthropologist Gustave Le Bon. Gustave Le Bon, in his book entitled The Psychology of the Masses, discusses the people that make up the mass, whomever they are. He states that regardless of whether their manner of life, work force, character, or intellect is similar or different, **the fact that they have formed a throng instills some type of collective spirit in them.** The majority of people have what are known as "**collective-social hallucinations.**" There are several instances of societal illusions like this throughout history, and one might make the argument that thousands of individuals at the same time were aware of them.

Keywords: *Collective Spirit, Collective-Social-Hallucinations, Social Delusions*

Gustave Le Bon and the Psychology of the Masses

It is possible to accept the following as the primary theses of the psychology of the masses, which was begun by Gustave Le Bon: The person, lured by the crowd and exposed to

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the unconscious, regresses to the fundamental stage of humanity, indulging in the most common inclinations. This happens because the individual is exposed to the unconscious. The "psychological crowd" is a concept coined by Gustave Le Bon with the intention of illuminating the actual meaning of the term "crowd" for the very first time. A "psychological crowd" is a certain mental and emotional condition that people might be in. The mob has just one soul, which is a collective soul, which of course has fleeting personalities, but characters that are quite clear. As a result, unity is the defining feature of the crowd. "It constitutes a single entity and is subject to the law of the mental unity of the multitudes." In accordance with this rule, the thoughts and emotions of the total may be understood at any given moment. Instead, in a sense that is more or less permanent, it becomes the sentiments and ideas of its component parts: "the conscious personality disappears, and the sentiments and ideas of all units are directed in the same direction." According to Le Bon, the emergence of "crowds" establishing a collective "spirit" is what paved the way for the formation of democracy. The person has the potential to take on the role of "leader" within the context of it, particularly if he believes he will be able to do so due to the fact that the crowd has an essential need to shape and act on them. Le Bon's two-pronged notion that nothing can be ruled better than crowds and that their power resides in their humility both have the same base, which is the presence of the leader: "Their thirst for obedience makes them instinctively submit to those who proclaim themselves their masters." According to the author, these new lords or leaders "gained more complete acquiescence from the crowd than any government has." Le Bon advocated for a new social ideal that might constructively organize crowds and contribute to the formation of a new civilisation. This is because the rising of the crowds is an indication that they are preparing for the approaching demise of our civilization.

Sigmund Freud & the Führer and Mass Psychology

Freud, on the other hand, has questioned the opposition or distinction between individual psychology and social psychology or mass psychology, society regarded to be multifarious and composite, or at least constructed, from the very beginning of his career.

From the perspective of the notion of mass, we may investigate the function of tyrants. It is because they are an indication of the "spirit of the times" (Zeitgeist) that Fuhrers like Hitler are able to impose themselves on their populations. The era of fascism has self-professed itself to be the age of the masses, or more specifically, the age of the masses that have been bewitched or persuaded by the leaders (Fuhrer, etc.). One of the chapters of the important book that was posthumously released by the sociologist Max Weber in 1921 was dedicated to charismatic control. of this chapter, Weber named, via the notion of "charisma," the attributes of a personality that "make it perceive him as a leader." Since he possesses supernatural, superhuman, or at the very least uncommon abilities and traits (ability), he gives off the impression of being a messenger of God or a model human being when he is shown to the general public.

It was not necessary for him to have direct personal contact with contemporary mass movements or fascist leaders (Fuhrer) in order for him to reject this manner of dominance on a theoretical level. He was aware that the form of charisma studied by sociologists, this "revolutionary power," had been brought into an era that was still marked by tradition, and he believed that this charisma could organize a transformation, hence a "change of direction." During the complete reorientation of all attitudes towards the various spheres of life and the world in general actions and ideas".

When looking at history, it can be seen that the idea of the "Fuhrer" spread throughout the nationalist youth movement in Germany beginning in the 1890s. This concept was surrounded by a vision of a world in which different philosophical, social, and aesthetic theories were mixed, with the idea that there would be "unity" (the Bund). In the social reality of the post-war period, which asserted a way of life superior to the present modern society, this

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concept of the Fuhrer began to overlap with the concept of the mass he would rule; The Spanish philosopher Ortega y Gasset's (1883-1955) work on the "Uprising of the Masses" published in 1929, *The lonely crowd*, is based on the fact that the "mass" is perceived as a new phenomenon as well as alarming, at least in the You will be able to give your testimony. The mass is significant not only for its very unique numeric dimension, but also for the fact that it shows individuals who, having entered a time of lethargy, escaped in the semi independent domains of the bourgeois or the aristocratic. Both of these factors contribute to the mass's notability. It would seem that the people at large were able to have their concerns heard, if not through their own voices, then at the very least by the words of the leaders whom they praised.

Sigmund Freud passed away around this time, in the year 1920. He claimed to have gathered materials for the study of mass psychology when he was on holiday in Gastein, but he was not prepared to invest in "these deep problems." Biographer Peter Gay characterizes Freud as adhering to "an outmoded political liberalism." According to Freud, Freud was rather condescending toward these "stupid (moron) people," and he preferred to apply his psychoanalysis to leaders and masses. Freud was not engaged in politics to any other degree. It is equally legitimate to think that Freud was interested in politics from another angle, suggesting that he looked at it from another angle that gave him access to the unconscious conditions of political action and allowed them to come to light. This interpretation demonstrates that Freud reasoned on the basis of functional categories that the biographer deemed necessary. As a result, his work "The Disturbance in Civilization" (*Le malaise dans la Civilisation*), which was published in 1930, was able to show itself as a treatise that was not frightened of comparison with the classics of political philosophy, particularly due to the fact that it mobilized them and developed their ideas. There arose the issue of building a "mass psychology" by capturing them as members of a "people, caste, state, institution, or crowd of people" organized in the form of a "mass psychology." This led to the question of whether or not a "mass psychology" could be established. After the end of the First World War, the common people and the political figures who represented them were at the forefront of public opinion throughout Europe. Anger at each

and every one of his public performances, whether it was the agitators of the post-war era in Germany and Austria, the communist leaders of revolutionary Russia, or the brilliant, weak electoral performance of Benito Mussolini, an Italian politician who had transitioned from socialism to a warmongering, nationalist, and anti-union stance. Through its activities against the unions and industrial occupations, Mussolini's "unions" battle, which began in March 1919, wreaked havoc on the working class in 1920. This was accomplished by wrestling the working class into submission.

Le Bon And Freud And The Fuhrer

Based on his critical interpretation of Gustave Le Bon's works, he offers an analysis of the connection that exists between the common people and the Fuhrer. According to Freud, a person who gets caught up in the mass is characterized by heightened emotional activity, reduced intellectual performance, and therefore might result in overt disinhibition. Freud also argues that the majority of the work on mass psychology that he encountered deployed the notion of "associative power" (Suggestion), but he accepted this phenomena as an incompressible truth. Freud's acceptance of this phenomenon stems from the fact that he saw it as an incompressible fact. Freud returns to this subject thirty years after his own experience in this field. When he was a young doctor at the Paris Salpêtrière, he took part in the well-known Bernheim evocation exercises with the goal of overcoming this phenomenon, the foundations of which he had planned to analyze. By activating his theory of the libidinal in this context, he seeks to examine the strong emotional bond that unites people in the masses. In order to understand what drives people to conform to Others rather than oppose them, two particularly illustrative examples of "artificial mass" should serve to illustrate the question. Church and State both. One of the challenges is being able to tell the difference between the masses who are led and the masses that do not have a leader. In addition to roles and hierarchies, the structure of these two groups is based on "a mirage of which there is a supreme authority - Jesus Christ

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for the Catholic Church, the Commander of the Army - that loves every individual who makes up the mass equally."

Ordu adheres to an analogous line of reasoning, if not the identical one: The connection between these individuals is similar to that of a brotherhood that is founded on a shared affection for a father figure; however, the most significant distinction is that the hierarchical structure of Ordu shows the "father" role at all levels. The move from the history of ideas to a thesis that states they would pull the unity of Armies out of love for notions like as nation or honor is something that Freud is opposed to. It called into question the concept that ideas could take the place of a respected connection between military commanders and the people under their command, and it brought to mind the severe neuroses brought on by the First World War that were noticed inside the German Army. The essential psychological mechanism that drives members of an audience to connect with a leader or Fuhrer and with each other is based on one of two potential connections that individuals may relate to with others: either in the shape of the object of their wants or in the form of an Other one seeks to mimic. This mechanism pushes members of an audience to connect with a leader or Fuhrer and with each other. When the kid is young and experiencing the Oedipal constellation, which occurs when the youngster desires to have the mother so that they may be like the father, these two possibilities might be helpful. Freud arrives at the conclusion that "identification" rather than "objektwahl" (fixation on an object) is the fundamental mode of the development of emotions.

It is an emotional form that may replace a libidinal fixation with a failed object when the individual integrates the object of want into his or her own identity (Self). It is possible for this to happen when the individual has failed to fulfill the desire object. Empathy and the internal creation of a personal ideal, known as a "Self ideal," are both made possible by identification. The desire to want to be like an Other may naturally lead to slippage, particularly when one is no longer happy with integrating the object of adoration into the ideal of the inner Self, but instead starts to seek it that way. This is especially true when the desire to want to be like an Other leads to slippage. When two individuals, particularly young people, fall in love,

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something might happen to them. something is very common in young people. At the end of the day, everything boils down to whether the "object is with the Self or supersedes the Self ideal." To put it another way, it all depends on whether the loved one is accepted as someone who the individual wants to be like at all costs, or whether the wishes and desires of the loved one completely replace the motivations of the individual concerned. The issue that has to be answered is whether or not he will accept it. In point of fact, this condition is not so unlike to that of hypnosis, and it is comparable to the emotion of love in that it is marked by "submissive devotion, meekness, and the absence of criticism." One thing that love and identification have in common is that they are both expressions of sexuality that are suppressed. These are the urges that might manifest themselves when it is difficult to experience instant fulfillment. Freud solved the mystery of evocative power by understanding the structural link between hypnosis and the development of a mass. This power rests in the fact that people emerge from the intricate web of interconnected ties that they retain at the precise time the mass is produced.

As was notably evident in Nazi Germany, the people publicly attest to the desire to replace their own personality (Self) with that of a Beyond, to commit themselves totally to a Self other than their own, and so as to give up control of their own existence. This desire was especially prevalent during the time period of the Third Reich. Freud did not continue to investigate the issue of mass creation via the hypnotic replacement of the Self (not the ideal of the Self) by the object; nevertheless, he did continue to research the theory of the masses, owing to the study of the notion of "herd psychology," which is often seen in popular literature.

Freud gives this description of the way in which children identify with one another: "Their first demands are fairness, equal treatment for all." If it is true that you cannot be a favorite, then you can be certain that no one else will choose you as their favorite either. This impulse was also at the basis of the "community spirit" that existed in society, particularly in the early days of this spirit. Freud eventually recreated the political conduct that related to this approach, and it went something like this: "No one should come forward, everyone should be the same and have the same thing." To practice social justice, one must be willing to forego a

great number of goods in order to ensure that others are not forced to do the same or demand that they do so. In 1920, a year that was significant for political upheaval and change throughout Europe, Freud held this opinion. He is of the opinion that a "demand for social justice is the root of social ethics and the spirit of responsibility"

Evaluation and Conclusion

The transition of antagonistic sentiments into a very positive identification with others, motivated by the desire to not be worse off than they are, gives birth to social feelings. However, there is one exception to this rule, and that is the leader, a more superior person through whom everyone wants to be controlled. This is done, for example, by activating emotional bonds similar to thwarted homosexual love, through mass organization that emerges in the church or the military. This can be interpreted as a critique of patriarchal culture that systematically excludes women and their life projects. The Freudian outline of mass psychology can also be interpreted as a critique of mass psychology as a critique of patriarchal culture. In point of fact, does this not still hold true today? Differences, is it still feasible for us to move on Earth towards regression, and even to dream of constructing a civilization that will lead us forward? Differences.

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